

The susceptibility of Generation Z to machine learning on Social Media moderated by training a fake news context

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ABSTRACT

Due to the current popularity of Social Media and the hyper connectivity fake news currently spreads as ‘digital wildfire’. Gen Z, the population group that suffers the most exposure from fake news because of their vast online presence, is the focus group of this paper. Due to the amounts of data generated by users all over the world, in combination with the evolvement and widespread usage of machine learning to increase personalized desires, fake news is becoming more personalized than ever. This research is interested in the effect of machine learning within fake news on the susceptibility of Gen Z, and the impact that training on machine learning has on this relationship. Therefore, this research conducted in a lab experiment to determine whether training has an impact on the susceptibility, and whether this is a positive or negative impact.

Keywords

Machine Learning, algorithms, social media, fake news, Generation Z, training, susceptibility.

INTRODUCTION

While the coined term ‘fake news’ gained notoriety over the recent years, the actual distribution of misinformation goes back centuries. For example, in 1835, the New York Sun claimed that there was an alien civilization on the moon. This is known as the ‘Great Moon Hoax’. The consequence was that The New York Sun’s circulation rose significantly due to increased sensation, thereby establishing itself as a leading newspaper at the time (CiTS, n.d.). Today, fake news can be seen as ‘digital wildfire’ enabled by ‘hyper connectivity’ (World Economic Forum, 2013). With the popularization of Social Media through increased internet-access, new forms of communication arose (Willis, 2017). Current

generations can communicate and share information instantaneously and at a scale larger than ever before. A consequence of this development is the drastic increase in dissemination of fake news through a wider variety of channels worldwide, subsequently challenging journalistic norms (Soll, 2016) Therefore, the World Economic Forum believes fake news to be one of the biggest threats to governments and society (World Economic Forum, 2013). Fake news has become notoriously successful as a weapon to undermine democratic processes, due to the susceptible nature of humankind (Vasu, et al., 2018). Society is generally susceptible to misinformation because susceptibility relies on memory, emotions and bias (Matthews, 2019). The susceptibility of misinformation is thereby enhanced by the social mechanism that is Social Media, users tend to create a ‘social media bubble’ (Matthews, 2019). only getting in contact with desired people and organizations. The most susceptible targets according to research carried out by Adobe in the UK are born between 1995 and 2010, also dubbed Generation Z (Stewart, 2019). Even though “members of Generation Z are true digital natives” members of Generation Z are more likely to be influenced by online content (McCarthy, 2019). This could also be explained due to their unprecedented online presence, being online the most that is (Wagner, Mitter, & Korner, 12). However, in general, Generation Z is more likely to trust strangers, 61% trusts that what a stranger tells them is truthful and 50% of 12-15 year are likely to believe something when it’s on the internet (Ipsos, 2018). Due to the online presence and the vast amounts of data generated by generation Z, utilization of machine learning in social media has become very effective. Adding to the aforementioned ‘social media bubble’ by increasing the amount of probabilistically determined desired content shown. This is either promoted organizational or content generated by the platform’s algorithms. Machine learning algorithms are based on time, location, page content, recency,

frequency, and velocity of the user's interactions (Huang, Zhang, & Zhang, 2019). This means machine learning can discern patterns in user profiles that increase the probability for a positive response from these users to specific content (Bilenko, Richardson, & Tsai, 2011).

Social media users, especially younger ones, will likely become more affected by algorithmically generated content that holds misinformation, making believing and spreading fake news to peers more effective, adding fuel to wildfires. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the susceptibility of generation Z to machine learning on Social Media in a fake news context. Since it has become most important to counter the threat that is fake news, which is supposedly worsened by machine learning on social media platforms. The researchers are eager to find out whether training Generation Z in the general principles of machine learning, affects this susceptibility to fake news in social media generated for users by machine learning, in order to influence the amount of fake news that is distributed on social media.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

This research is conducted to identify the relationship between susceptibility of Generation Z to fake news and machine learning in Social Media, including the effect of training on the relationship between susceptibility and machine learning in Social Media.

Relevance

Academic Relevance

Conflicting literature with regards to susceptibility to fake news exists. While (Matthews, 2019) argues that susceptibility to false information is due to bias, emotion and memory, Rand & Pennycook argue that people are susceptible to fake news because of lack of reasoning (Rand & Pennycook, 2018). Other studies remain convinced that the social aspect of social media and the lack of fact checking by individuals and distributors remains generally low. This means that there are a significant number of variables that influence susceptibility. The fact is that people remain susceptible to misinformation. Due to the amounts of data generated by users all over the world, in combination with the involvement and widespread usage of machine learning to increase personalized desires, it is interesting to study the effects of machine learning in Social Media to susceptibility, especially to study the younger generation, generation Z. However, there is little to no research about susceptibility to machine learning, either because of its obvious influence or the focus of institutions lies elsewhere. This does not mean however, that it is not a necessity to study the

effect of machine learning on susceptibility. For studies to focus on countering machine learning to prevent more fake news being spread, research must be carried out on that has influence on the relationship between susceptibility and machine learning. Therefore, this study will focus on how the relationship between susceptibility of Generation Z to fake news and machine learning can be affected by means of training in machine learning. Therefore, the effects of machine learning to susceptibility needs to be studied in order to be able to influence this research the effect training has on the relationship. This paper builds on research from (Wagner, Mitter, & Korner, 12) that studied the effect of Generation Z on Twitter to bots as a challenge. Since this is not necessarily comparable to this study, it can be concluded that the academic relevance lies in studying a new context within susceptibility to fake news. Also prompting other researchers to investigate susceptibility to machine learning, as to counter fake news.

Managerial Relevance

If training in machine learning affects the susceptibility of Generation Z to fake news in Social Media, policy makers and governmental bodies would benefit directly from a limitation in the spread of fake news on social media. Making this research valuable to policy makers worldwide, seeing as governmental proceedings are under great threat from Fake News, as stated in the introduction. Machine learning algorithms are evolving, becoming more effective (Jhingran, 2019). Thereby further threatening to worsen the status quo with regards to fake news. Moreover, the general public is protected from becoming more and more susceptible as machine learning evolves over time. The idea is that the general public will be able to withstand algorithmically created content, based on their input, by training them. Lastly, there is managerial relevance for businesses willing to participate in training individuals and organizations affected by decreased effectiveness of algorithmic targeting as well as the Social Media if regulations were to be sharpened or adjusted with regards to training or implementation of algorithms on social media platforms.

The problem statement of this research is as follows:

“To what extent does machine learning in Social Media affect the susceptibility of Generation Z to fake news, and to what extent is this relationship influenced by training in machine learning?”

To be able to answer this question, there are different theoretical and practical research questions on which the research focuses:

Theoretical research questions:

- What is machine learning?
- How can machine learning in social media be defined?
- How can susceptibility to machine learning in social media be defined?
- How can susceptibility to fake news through machine learning on social media be measured?
- How can training in machine learning be used to influence susceptibility to machine learning?

Practical research questions:

- To what extent does machine learning influence the susceptibility of Generation Z to fake news on social media?
- To what extent does training on machine learning influence the susceptibility of Generation Z to fake news generated by machine learning?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This research aims to find out to what extent the training in machine learned content influences the susceptibility of Generation Z with or without creating awareness and to what extent is the susceptibility of Generation Z influenced by awareness of machine learned content. Machine learning content can be defined as every piece of online content with a machine learning algorithm behind it. Machine learning is defined as “an evolving branch of computational algorithms that are designed to emulate human intelligence by learning from the surrounding environment” (Naqa & Murphy, 2015)

Susceptibility has numerous definitions, in this paper the definition of susceptibility will be defined based on the paper of (Parrish, Bailey, & Courtney, 2009) that focuses on susceptibility of phishing attacks. In this paper susceptibility is defined as “the likelihood that a person will respond to a phishing attack”. Similarly, this study defines susceptibility in the context of machine learned content as the likelihood that a person will respond to machine learning content. The phishing study is used because phishing has the same purpose as most machine learning content apart from the fact that phishing is meant to harm a person.

Susceptibility can be affected by several different variables, as previously stated. One for example is the gender of a subject (Parrish, Bailey, & Courtney, 2009). This research only focuses the variable machine learning and the effect of machine learning on susceptibility.

Susceptibility of machine learned content can be measured via the same constructs that are used to

measure the susceptibility to phishing attacks. Companies often use a series of tests called a decision tree learning algorithm to test how susceptible their employees are to phishing attacks (Moore, n.d.). These types of tests could be modified to fit the circumstances that are necessary to measure the susceptibility to machine learned content before and after training.

Training to influence the awareness of machine learned content, and there for possibly influence the relationship between machine learning and its susceptibility, can be done by adopting techniques that are used to mitigate the susceptibility to phishing. The best way to protect employees against phishing is to educate them and to conduct training sessions that use mock phishing scenarios .

In figure 1, the conceptual model. It can be noted that the independent variable machine learning directly influences the dependent variable susceptibility. Training in machine learning content influences the relationship between machine learning and susceptibility of machine learning content.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Hypotheses

Based on the conceptual model, several hypotheses are derived as follows:

Direct effect:

- H1: Machine learning in social media positively affects susceptibility to fake news by Generation Z

Interaction effect:

- H2: The relationship between machine learning on social media and susceptibility to fake news of Generation Z is negatively affected training in machine learning.

METHODS

Data collection/Research design

Data is collected using a laboratory experiment in which variables to be tested are isolated. Thus, enabling for a precise measure of the exact effect the independent variable may have on the dependent variable. Additionally, it allows to eliminate extraneous variables that may interfere with the results of the experiments (Sawyer, Worthing, & E, 1979). Furthermore, lab experiments allow for replicability of the research, as the exact environmental conditions can be clearly outlined in future research (Karl, 2016).

The lab experiment, the variables of ‘machine learning’ and ‘training’ on the susceptibility of Generation Z participants are tested through means of two chosen control groups. Specifically, the simulation experiment technique is applied to create a setting/environment that closely represents a natural environment in which similar activities take place. (Sawyer, Worthing, & E, 1979)

This is conducted using a self-constructed decision-making tree, based on ID3 tree learning (Jazuli, 2018). During the experiment, choices that each participant picks are observed and analyzed afterwards. In the article about the susceptibility of people towards phishing, the susceptibility is tested by measuring how many people click on the phishing link. Like the article, the same kind of construct can be used to measure the susceptibility to machine learning. However, instead of clicking the link, users will be tested on whether they believe a certain statement on a certain topic. With machine learning integrated in the decision tree these statements will be modified to best influence the users. Based on whether they believe a false statement or think a true statement is false, susceptibility will be measured. The decision tree used in this research can be found in the model to the right.

Figure 2. Mimicked predictive algorithm, based on ID3

The decision tree starts with asking the participant if they are familiar with a certain subject. If the participant is familiar with the subject, he/she will receive no context. If the participant is not familiar, he/she will receive context on the subject. After this 'setup' the decision tree consists of three repetitive steps. The initial step is a statement on a certain topic, this statement can either be true or false. The statement is true for people who are familiar with the subject or, in repetitive steps, people who were correct about the previous statement. The statement is false for people who are not familiar with the subject or, in repetitive steps, people who were incorrect about the previous statement. In the second step the participant will be asked whether he or she agrees or disagrees with the statement. In the third step the participant will receive false or no context on the subject, based on their answer.

In the case that participants answer correctly, the decision tree acts like a machine learning device, the knowledge of the participant will be noted and further tested by providing an additional true statement which will test the knowledge of the participant again. If the participant is correct, the decision tree will provide no further context and true statements that are more difficult to discern whether it is true or false until the participant is incorrect. When this happens, the participant will be tested on their susceptibility of false content with false statements. If participants are often correct the grade of machine learning will intensify until the limit of a person's knowledge on a subject is reached and the decision tree can start testing their susceptibility.

If the participant is incorrect, he or she will be provided with false context and a false statement to observe whether the participant agrees or disagrees with the false statement. In the case that the participant agrees with the false statement he or she will receive one 'susceptibility point'. If a participant is correct, he or she will receive no 'susceptibility point'.

A participant that is incorrect early in the decision tree is more susceptible for machine learning than a participant that is incorrect in a later stage of the experiment and will therefore rank up more 'susceptibility points' the longer the decision tree continues. More points indicate that the participant is more likely to be susceptible to machine learning. A participant that disagrees with a true statement will not receive any points but will be tested with false context and a false statement in the following step. This is because people who disagree with true statements are more skeptical and thus less susceptible. People who believe false statements are more gullible and thus more susceptible. The same phenomenon can also be seen in ads, consumers with high ad skepticism may be impossible to persuade by means of information or argument

because they will not believe any stated claims. (Obermiller & Spangenberg, 1998)

The experiment

The experimental design used is the factorial design, where one independent variable is measured with a moderating variable in this research the variables 'Machine learning' and 'Training'. This resembles the pre-test-post-test control group design.

Initially, participants are split in two separate groups, group A and B. Both groups are provided with a decision-making tree to analyze their initial choices. Measured in susceptibility points. After this first case, group A will be provided with training and education on what algorithm is used in this experiment and the implementation of algorithms that may take place in their daily life. Group B will not receive this additional training when participating in the second round of the experiment.

The training consists of informing the participants about what machine learning is, and how it is implemented. Additionally, participants will be educated on how to recognize specific elements that could indicate an implementation of machine learning in the information that the participants receive. Like the first round, choices of participants are once again observed. However, the focal point in this round is to observe whether the training has altered the decisions being made in group A and the difference in results compared to the first round of the experiment and group B. Two cases will be provided on the plastic problem and 5G & Huawei, based on the decision tree model above.

The initial step is to provide a topic question, to determine whether the participants are knowledgeable on the topic. In general, if a participant answered a statement correctly that is either true or false, no additional context is provided. For participants answering incorrectly, the machine learning process is implemented by providing additional false context to analyze how susceptible they are to false information. Deeper in the algorithm, participants that answer correctly at every step, are tried to be made more susceptible by providing manipulated context that is richer in detail, where falsehoods are less discernible.

Sample

Population for this study consists of participants that are within the age group of Generation Z. The sampling frame consists of all adolescents or youngsters born between 1995-2010. For this research, the non-probability convenient sampling method is applied. Participants are chosen based on the ease of approach and availability in the vicinity of the researchers. The sample consists of students

from the Tilburg University and/or people acquainted to the researchers that fit within the age requirement.

To provide, to some extent, applicable data. 6 participants are chosen between participants are between the ages of 18-24. This due to the strict requirement in research with minor aged participants, where consent of the participants' guardians/parents will be required to comply with the ethical research requirements of conducting research with minor aged participants. (The Informed Consent Process with Children, n.d.)

To determine the exact sample size needed, the saturation sampling method is to be applied. This indicates that based on the data that is has been collected (in this case the number of participants in the sample), further sampling would not be necessary as researchers sees similar results repeatedly (Saunders, et al., 2017).

Validity & Reliability

Internal validity

As the study takes place in a lab, artificial setting it enables the researchers to control the variables (machine learning & training) and exclude extraneous variables that may affect the criterion variable. Therefore, the internal validity is adequate. In addition, in this setting it enables the researchers to draw valid conclusions about the possible correlational/causal effect that takes place (training having a positive/negative influence on the susceptibility of Generation Z on machine learning content). Additionally, a control group is included in the experiment. Thereby, limiting the effect of maturation.

External validity

The external validity in this lab experiment is generally low, as the setting is an artificial one here the variables are being manipulated/controlled by the researchers. Additionally, as the sample size consists of only students from Tilburg University and is not adequate/large enough, the results cannot be automatically generalized for the population of interest, members of Generation Z. Furthermore, the results obtained may only be partially applicable to Generation Z in the Netherlands and results may vary across countries.

Reliability

To increase the reliability, the experiment is test-retested. Thereby, enabling the stability of the research as the experiment is tested beforehand before the actual experiment is conducted. Hence, enabling the researchers to ensure that similar results are obtained during the experiments.

RESULTS

The lab experiment was conducted among 6 participants from the Gen Z target group that were divided into two groups, group A and group B. All participants in both groups received the same test case in the first round of the experiment. Group A scored an average of 2.33 out of 3 susceptibility points, making them rather susceptible to machine learning according to the standards of the experiment. Group B received an average score of 2 out of 3 susceptibility points, making them rather susceptible to machine learning but a bit less susceptible than group A. Therefore, it can be stated that hypothesis 1 is correct, indicating that machine learning increases the susceptibility of Generation Z on fake news. The applied cases can be found at Zenodo.org, through 'Rens Bueters'.

After this first round group A received training about machine learning, teaching them how it works and how it is implemented. Also receiving tips on how to recognize machine learning, in a news context, based on their input. Group B received no training.

After the training the experiment was conducted again with a new case, both groups received the same test case in the second round of the experiment. Group A scored an average of 1.67 out of 3 susceptibility points. Group B received an average score of 1.67 out of 3 susceptibility points as well. Therefore, it can be stated that the second hypothesis, training has a negative effect on the susceptibility, is true. Thus, training, however basic, reduces the susceptibility of members of Gen Z to fake news.

When comparing the results of the first and second round of group A and B both groups scored better on the second round. However, group A's score decreased more than group B's score. This could indicate that training has a negative effect on the susceptibility of machine learning. When taking a closer look at the experiment participants with a good (read: low) susceptibility score, often score these points at the end of the experiment. This could indicate that machine learning has a positive effect on the susceptibility of machine learning among Generation Z participants.

DISCUSSION

When creating the method that would be used for conducting the experiment for the research there where a significant amount of points of discussion on how to best simulate the effect machine learning on social media has on the susceptibility of Generation Z to fake news. There are two methods of implementing machine learning within the

experiment. The first method was to integrate machine learning inside the actual experiment, which was the option that was eventually picked for the experiment. The second method was to conduct a questionnaire beforehand and adapt the experiment based on the answers from the participant. Option one was eventually picked as the best option because there were certain limitations to option two. The first problem was that when implementing option two, each participant would need a modified case. This would not only have a negative effect on the scalability of the experiment but also create unreliable results since each participant had a slightly different case. The second problem with option two was the measuring of the effect of machine learning. Since machine learning is an ongoing process, only implementing it beforehand with a small questionnaire would not be realistic. These two problems did not apply on option one.

To increase the level of machine learning two adaptations can be implemented. The first adaptation would be replacing the ‘true or false’ option within the experiment with a 5 or a 7-point Likert scale. First, this would result in a more precise grading of susceptibility points, which is now binary but could be on a scale to 5 or 7. This aspect of the adaptation will also create more precise results. Secondly, the level machine learning would increase since the statement following the answer of the participant can be based on 5 or 7 different answers instead of 2. This increases the level of machine learning because it would generate more personalized content. The second adaptation would be altering the amount of statements, the number of columns within the model. First, this would result in a more chances for the participants to receive susceptibility points, which will also create more precise results. Secondly, the level of machine learning will increase since the amount of statements that can be tested within the experiment has a positive effect on the grade of personalization within the statements.

Initially, the assumption was that only training would be an influence on the relationship between machine learning on social media and susceptibility to fake news of Generation Z. It was not considered that participants would already possess a certain level of skepticism, which would affect how susceptible the participants would be to the (additional) information provided. As mentioned previously in the paper, if a participant would have a high level of skepticism, it would likely be that they would dismiss any statement in the experiment to be true. Therefore, it can be stated that skepticism would both have an influence on the relationship between machine-learning and susceptibility and

would have a direct influence on the susceptibility of the participants.

Limitations

However, there are certain limitations to the experiment. These are mostly due to a time constraint that was given to the research. When having unlimited time to conduct the research at hand, certain adaptations would be made to increase the level of machine learning within the experiment and to create results that would enable the researcher to draw a reliable conclusion. Overall an algorithm is mimicked, not created, thereby limiting the internal validity of the experiment. Additionally, due to the time constraint, the initial intend to pre-test the experiment beforehand to ensure reliability was not possible.

Furthermore, with the current sample size it is not possible to generalize the findings to the population at interest, members of Generation Z. As the results are only based on a sample size in The Netherlands, findings may differ when research is conducted in other countries.

Additionally, as a factorial experimental design is applied - which resembles an pretest-posttest control group design - this may affect the behavior of participants, as the possibility increases that participants recognizes certain elements from the previous case. Hence, the results of the measured effects may also be affected as participants may see more details in the experiment that the population in a natural setting would not notice. Which in term, also affects the generalizability of the experiment.

To directly increase the reliability of the results two adaptations can be implemented. The first adaptation would be to weighted scoring of susceptibility points. This would be implemented by giving more points to participants who prove to be susceptible at the beginning of the experiment than participants who are susceptible near the end of the experiment. When looking at the model that is used to perform the experiment, susceptibility points in the first column of statements would weigh high in the scoring and this would decrease per column.

The second adaptation would be implementing a satisfactory sampling method. Because of the time limit that this research was bound to, the experiment could only be conducted among 6 participants. In the case that there would be no time limit, a satisfactory sampling method should be implemented to ensure the most reliable results.

For future research, it is recommended to conduct similar experiments with a larger number of participants to reach an adequate sample size to gain results that are representative and generalizable.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the conducted experiments, it can be concluded that the training of educating members of Generation Z on what machine learning is, how it is implemented, and how one can recognize that the information being presented has been adjusted by machine learning to reduce the susceptibility of members of Generation Z was effective. As the average score decreased from group A, which has received the training, from 2.33 out of 3 in the first round of the experiment to 1.67 out of 3 in the second round.

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